

A Collaborative Critical Reflection: ‘No Student Should Be Left Behind’ – Efforts Towards Equality And Quality In The ‘New Normal’

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Abstract

Online learning is not new to the world. However, seemingly to lecturers at higher education institutions in South Africa, it indeed presented itself as experientially new due to demands of a radical transition forced by the Covid-19 pandemic. The call to ‘no student is to be left behind’ in South Africa at the start of the Covid-19 pandemic, in pursuit of equality and quality increased professional demands. However, universities in South Africa differ in equality in many respects which include access to technology and digital literacy. This paper presents a comparative structured reflection of four lecturers (two females and two males) from three different universities in South Africa, exploring the imposed ‘new experience’ and what factors were associated with the sudden shift to online learning. The process involved an individual structured self-reflection at the end of the semester guided by a collaboratively developed questionnaire. A comparative critical review and qualitative analysis collaborated through the group’s community of practice followed. The results evidenced that in reality, online teaching was not implemented in the true sense but rather forms of technology were used in teaching and learning. Identified factors associated with efforts to achieve equality and quality of teaching and learning during the Covid-19 lockdown include personal and professional transformation, a better understanding of student context and background, innovative teaching and assessment, active trans-institutional learning and professional collegial support even if it was informal. The article further raises caution that equality and quality are a collaborative responsibility of all primary stakeholders.

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic forced a radical shift to a ‘new normal’ from face-to-face learning to online learning at higher education institutions almost overnight within varying personal, professional and geographical contexts. While online learning is not new to the world, to many lecturers at higher education institutions in the south, it indeed presented itself as experientially new due to demands of a radical transition. Students registered for face-to-face learning at physical contact institutions were also ‘forced’ into the new mode. The call of ‘no student is to be left behind’ in South Africa at the start of the COVID-19 pandemic, in pursuit of equality, is in itself demanding especially where universities in the south differ in equality in many respects such as in infrastructure and resources, the level of available technology and its maximum use amongst lecturers and students, and enrolled student populations of markedly different economic and social backgrounds, amongst others. The manifestation of societal in-equality cannot be compartmentalised, as seen in the attempt to respond to the COVID-19 pandemic. The demands to realise the ideal is not congruent to the challenges faced in reality, as elucidated in a number of studies in education around the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic (Aristovnik, 2020; Hedding, et al. 2020; Konig, et al. 2020). Inequalities can also be perceived as having access to technology but not having the skill to use it, challenges in connection to use technology and not having access to appropriate technological devices for learning at all. This has created a topical gap in understanding how lecturers negotiated the ‘new online experience’ and what promotes or hinders the sudden shift to the ‘new experience’. This study aimed to understand the demands and challenges faced by lecturers imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic and the national call for equality through ‘no student is to be left behind’ to culminate in sharing strategies with the higher education fraternity during times of radical shifts and of more planned transitions.

Online learning is likely to be an essential facet of the ‘new normal’ post the COVID-19 pandemic (Chaka, 2020; Mittal, et al. 2020). While there may be common inputs from the wider sector, the experiences and learnings of varying contexts enrich the body of knowledge, with the inherent potential to raise further questions, affirm experiences and provide new insights for introspection and reflection. Structured reflection on

the thrust to ‘no student is to be left behind’ and ‘save the academic year’ is an effective and authentic way to provide insights and learnings to further negotiate the journey through the ‘new normal’ and the future. Reflective practice embraces experience regarding challenging situations; reflective practice with co-operative enquiry in small groups of individuals can deepen the level of reflection (Caley, et al. 2017). This paper presents a structured reflection of four lecturers (two females and two males) from three different universities in South Africa who negotiated their teaching and learning during the COVID-19 lockdown, in a bid, like many other lecturers, to heed the call to ‘no student is to be left behind’. The link to the four participants was a common colleague who realised the need for greater trans-institutional professional collegial support, albeit informally. The study involved transdisciplinary contexts as the lecturers were based respectively in the Faculty of Science and Faculty of Education. The study aimed to answer the following reflective research questions:

1. Comparatively, how did lecturers from different universities approach the digital necessity during the COVID -19 pandemic?
2. What were the key challenges to the digital necessity experienced by the lecturers in higher education?
3. What are key factors associated with efforts to achieve quality and equality of teaching and learning to negotiate the digital necessity resulting from the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic?

Literature Review

The COVID-19 pandemic catapulted universities in South Africa to re-think teaching and learning to accommodate the use of technology in online teaching. Lecturers across institutions have had to re-structure their teaching either informally or formally to facilitate active and successful learning among their diverse student population. Lecturers were forced into remote teaching and learning, paving the way for introducing online learning, illustrating a paradigm shift in the way educators deliver quality education (Dhawan, 2020). There is no one-size-fits-all pedagogy for online learning. There is a variety of subjects with varying needs. Different subjects and age groups require different approaches to online learning (Doucet, et al. 2020).

Although online learning is often coarsely viewed as course content delivered online, it also incorporates web-based learning, computer-mediated learning and blended learning. Singh and Thurman (2019) define online learning as learning experiences in synchronous or asynchronous environments using different devices (e.g. mobile phones, laptops) with internet access. In these environments, students can be anywhere (independent) to learn and interact with instructors and other students (Singh and Thurman, 2019). The synchronous learning environment is structured in the sense that students attend live lectures, there are real-time interactions between educators and learners, and there is a possibility of instant feedback, whereas asynchronous learning environments are not properly structured. In such a learning environment, learning content is not available in the form of live lectures or classes; it is available at different learning systems and forums (Littlefield, 2018). Wasimet al. (2014) state that web-based learning is often called online learning or E-learning because it includes online course content. Discussion forums via email, videoconferencing, and live lectures (video streaming) are all possible through the web. Computer-Mediated Learning is facilitated through the use of electronic mail, computer networks and the Internet, simultaneously allowing opportunities for interaction.

Online learning has featured prominently in distance education but with the onset of the global COVID-19 pandemic, it has become more significantly relevant now as a tool for access to remote teaching and learning, more especially for traditional face-to-face higher education institutions that were forced to shift their mode of curricula delivery and assessment practices.

Online/e-Learning is an educational practice that is enhanced by the convergence of internet, computer and mobile technologies (Ndebele, 2020). It is ‘flexible learning using Information Communications Technology (ICT) resources, tools and applications, focusing on; accessing information, interaction amongst teachers, students and the online environment, collaborative learning, and production of materials, resources and learning experiences’ (Department of Education, 2004: 15). ICT practices range from emailing to online journaling, networked libraries, administration and developing creative software packages for the management of information tasks in teaching, examination and researching (Bagarukayo and Kalema, 2015: 168).

There has been much dependence and use of technologies such as Zoom, Microsoft platforms, Skype, Blackboard, Kaltura and Google Classroom, together with institutions’ own web-based software platforms called Learning Management Systems (LMS). Most academic and administrative staff use available LMSs to develop and upload module content, assess and measure student performance, track student progress and generate progress reports and feedback. Blended learning is the integration of face-to-face and online instruction (Graham, 2013). An example of blended learning is the flipped classroom approach, a pedagogical approach where direct instruction is flipped from a group learning space to an individual learning space.

The move to the online platform has been challenging for staff who have limited knowledge of educational technology. Online learning has had academic staff revisiting their teaching modes and assessments and re-evaluating their curricula (Hedding, et al. 2020; Rapanta, et al. 2020). According to Pather and Cupido (2020), ‘rapid transition resulted in academics having to learn new skills and new ways of doing and being and rethink ways of learning and teaching, while re-imagining new ways of delivering content online. The shift required academics to unlearn their old way of doing to adapt to new ways of teaching in which learning is active, responsive, and contextualized’. Online teaching and learning come in various modes: fully online, blended, hybrid and flipped classroom. The transition to ‘the new normal’ with its accompanying challenges of adaptation and implementation has been experienced in institutions across South Africa. In traditional face-to-face teaching, technology was generally incorporated to support classroom teaching, but with the practice of the ‘new normal’, it became mandatory, more especially in remote teaching scenarios and “academic staff had to rapidly prepare and capacitate themselves” (Motala and Menon, 2020: 80).

The pandemic has alerted academics to the need for innovation and flexibility in the teaching and learning environment. Moreover, the switch to online teaching has resulted in the need for greater collaboration among staff both within and across institutions in an effort to share narratives, personal experiences, pedagogies and reflexive practices to ensure that all students achieved equal access to teaching and learning. Using reflective practice as a framework, a study by Pather and Cupido (2020) examined the experiences of academics at a South African university as they transitioned to the new normal of online teaching and learning. The study highlighted the learning, unlearning and relearning processes and adaptation experiences of the academics. As staff started to unlearn old ways of doing, a pattern of resilience and commitment by academic staff developed. The pandemic also heightened academics’ need to teach with care and compassion, which strangely created a sense of connectedness with students which was not observable during face-to-face teaching. The learning and teaching approaches were carefully considered to ensure that ‘no student would be left behind’.

The sudden transition to online learning and its accompanying challenges are not only peculiar to higher education institutions nationally. A study undertaken by Almazova et al. (2020) to determine university teachers’ readiness for online education at a Polytechnic University in Russia identified the main hindrances being: computer literacy level, the university electronic environment and support, academic staff readiness and students’ readiness for online learning. In addition, Kebritchi et al.’s (2017) study that focuses specifically on issues and challenges faced in online teaching in higher education reveals three major categories of challenges related with instructors, learners, and content development. Their study suggests that in order to address these categories of challenges in online education, higher education institutions would be required to provide professional development for instructors, trainings for learners, and technical support for content development. Despite it being a democracy for more than two decades, South Africa is still characterised by inequality. Much of the university student population is therefore exposed to economic and essential public service disparities. The digital divide in South Africa is a reality. In the South African higher education context, the digital divide between students who have and do not have access to computers, internet and data has had a limiting impact on the viability of online learning. According to Maphalala et al. (2021), the digital divide can be bridged by connectivity; where there is no connectivity, it is difficult if not impossible for students in those areas to participate in online learning. This has been exacerbated by social and economic issues. The switch to online learning has also brought to fore the context of the student population enrolled at South African institutions. The digital divide is not merely about digital competency and exposure; it is also about having access to electricity, internet infrastructure and networks, data, and devices.

Online learning presents various challenges to higher education institutions in South Africa. For instance, many students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds do not have access to the internet due to the network coverage in rural areas (Jappie, 2020); and cannot connect to the internet even when the universities have made data available so that data costs are not the limiting factor. Similarly, findings in a US study conducted by Fishbane and Tomer (2020) related to students with no internet access during the pandemic indicates that as the level of poverty increases within that specific community, the rate of internet accessibilities declined rapidly. Thus these students with no or low socio-economic status struggle with affordability of broadband connection and are therefore most vulnerable to fall behind as they experience many challenges to network and easy link with others during online learning.

The sudden migration to online (or remote learning) has forced academic staff to improvise their teaching modes in often less than ideal situations, especially in a country such as South Africa, where university students do not have equal access to technologies used in online learning as well as equal access to data and connectivity. Staff were forced to design curricula that are responsive to online teaching and learning, for which academic

staff were expected to have both technical and pedagogical competence (Le Grange, 2004). Academic staff at contact universities might typically have little, if any, experience or training in the pedagogy or delivery of online learning. According to Internet World Stats (2020), as of 2019, only about thirty-nine percent of Africans have internet access compared to approximately eighty seven percent of Europeans and ninety-five percent of North Americans (Internet World Stats, 2020). In addition, Rohs and Ganz (2015) state that where there is access, there are further inequalities in bandwidth distribution, data price and internet speed, which are further shaped by socio-economic factors of gender, age, employment, educational background, neighbourhood and household income (Rohs and Ganz, 2015).

Where academic staff are ill-prepared to teach remotely with technology, arising from the sudden and compulsory switch to the use of technology, they are bound to struggle with manoeuvring online resources and digital tools, which can result in frustration and lowered self-esteem. Teaching staff of all backgrounds and ages have had to prepare and deliver their classes from home, with all the practical and technical challenges this entails, and often without proper technical support (Hodges, et al. 2020). Moreover, a significant challenge for university teachers has been their lack of the pedagogical content knowledge (Shulman, 1987) needed for teaching online (Ching, et al. 2018). Although technology has been shown to significantly impact learning outcomes, higher education institutions might have to increase academic support in using technology effectively. Chauhan et al. (2020) expand on this from two angles. From a hardware perspective, more video conferencing will require much more internet bandwidth, and therefore expanded and improved infrastructure. From a software perspective, educational institutions may need to improve faculty expertise for the increased focus on online delivery of instruction. This requires knowledge of software not just for video recording and video conferencing, but also for advanced functions such as working with virtual teams or remote monitoring of students during exams.

The transition to online learning has been encouraging especially since it gave academics the opportunity to interrogate, review and re-evaluate their curricula especially since the traditional teaching and assessment practices were no more as viable. Academics were compelled to upskill how they utilize online learning. Universities in South Africa initiated and implemented support measures for staff to engage with the online teaching and learning transition to ensure that no student is left behind. In addition, several institutions provided staff with data packages as well as training, counselling and research support via seminars and webinars. Nkosi et al. (2020) conducted a study exploring the pro-active measures undertaken by one such South African university (UKZN) to mediate the challenges of online learning and the lecturers' perceptions of how they traversed online learning. The study indicated that the lecturers embraced online learning positively, evidencing also high morale. Another South African qualitative interpretive case study (Mpungose, 2020) of 26 students reveal various challenges that hinder disadvantaged students from realising the full potential during online learning but the digital divide acts as the major hindrance. Furthermore, he advocates that since students are unevenly challenged they would require capacity building on the use of LMSs and other newly adopted online learning software.

Other studies have brought to fore other challenges. A study conducted by Kajiita et al. (2020) explored the preparedness, resources, institutional models, and attitudes and experiences of both the learners and the teaching staff towards remote online teaching and learning. Their study indicated that the lecturers were also not adequately prepared for remote teaching; even in the institutions where blended or technology enhanced learning takes place, the lecturers were still not fully equipped to engage in full online teaching. One of the reasons was that remote teaching and learning presented a completely new experience for traditional model universities, and therefore required a new set of skills altogether. This required proper planning and design to suit the needs of particular courses or modules. The study also indicated that the common adage of 'one size fits all' is a miscalculation or over-ambition for current remote online teaching and learning especially for practical courses.

Assessment is an integral part of teaching and learning (Rawlasyk, 2018; Kinzie, et al. 2014). Assessment is linked to module and curricula outcomes and goals. When the stakeholders of South Africa's higher education took the decision to continue with online teaching to ensure that higher learning was still feasible and to salvage the academic year, it went against the traditional norm of the face-to-face teaching and learning system. There was thus a need for academics to engage with their assessment practices that meant a switch to formative assessments (to monitor student learning and provide ongoing feedback) over summative assessments (where student learning is evaluated at the end of a unit or module by comparing against a standard or benchmark). Vonderwell et al. (2007) explain that online instruction requires a change in delivery modalities and by extension, adjusted formative and summative assessments to evaluate students' understanding of course content. However, challenges arise when lecturers attempt to tweak assessment techniques used in traditional face-to-

face classrooms to fit online instruction (Vonderwell, et al. 2007). Thus, due to a lack of preparation and the urgent move in shifting assessments remotely during the pandemic posed exceptional challenges for institutions of higher learning. Research evidence (Guangul, et al. 2020) from a recent case study of a Middle East College revealed that the main challenges of remote assessment identified during COVID-19 centered around academic dishonesty, infrastructure, coverage of learning outcomes, and commitment of students to submit assessments. However, they recommended that adopting combined evaluation methods for an assessment could be in favour towards the learning outcomes of the module, simultaneously minimizing the risk of academic dishonesty.

As a result of the coronavirus pandemic (COVID-19) South African universities across the country were compelled to rapidly advance from face-to-face to online learning. Due to the accelerated 'crisis' there was urgent need for reflective practice amongst academics within higher institutions of learning, thus the rationale behind this study which is underpinned by the critical reflection theory. The actual conception of reflective practice maybe attributed to Argyris and Schon (1976) and later to Schon (1983, 1987). More specifically, in relation to literature in education, research (Cranton, 1996) indicates the work of Dewey (1933) which is often cited as coming up with the idea of reflection.

Despite the fact that there is a plethora of theories that were used to reinforce the concept of critical reflection, this study mainly draws from Fook (2012) on how it can be used in the practice of learning and teaching in relation to improving professional practice and creating a platform for transformative actions. In this case, critical reflection augments and strengthens teaching and learning practices in an attempt to navigate through unsurmountable challenges. To further build on these conceptualisations, Fook (2015: 444) stresses that 'critical reflection is a way of researching one's personal practice or experience in order to develop our understandings of ourselves as knowers or makers of knowledge'. This resonates with our study. In addition, the critical reflection theory advocates improving capacity for research and knowledge-building (Hess, 1995:65), improved practice, the creation of new practice possibilities (Hess 1995, p.80) and an increased capacity to practise in change and uncertainty (Fook and Napier, 2000) which seem pertinent under these current circumstances. Killen (2016: 121) aptly conceptualises reflection as 'a form of enquiry through which educators can question their actions, the contexts in which they teach and on all the influences on those actions and contexts'. Our study involved a structured and deliberate effort for the lecturers to reflect on their teaching and learning through the pandemic, as will be elucidated in the methodology section.

Method

Research design

An interpretive paradigm underpinned the study. Within this paradigm, researchers aim to describe and understand the contexts in which participants respond, their circumstances and how they make meaning of their particular actions (Bertram and Christiansen, 2018). The study was a comparative qualitative study which involved four lecturers (two females and two males) from three different universities in South Africa. These lecturers, in a bid, like many other lecturers, negotiated their teaching and learning during the COVID-19 lockdown to heed the call to 'no student is to be left behind'. Three of the lecturers have doctoral qualifications with a minimum of twenty years of experience in education institutions and one has a masters as the highest qualification with six years of experience. The number of modules taught by the lecturers and student enrolment varied: 2 Modules (100), 1 module (436), 4 modules (160) and 2 modules (300).

The context of the universities differed in terms of campus infrastructure, resources and location. All are residential universities, with one in a rural location, one in an urban area and the other in a 'township' location. In South Africa, *township* describes a settlement which is often underdeveloped, with generally poor socio-economic conditions and which had been racially segregated during the period of apartheid. Townships are usually located on the periphery of urban areas.

Critical reflection-on-action (Killen, 2016) was used to frame the study. Critical reflection-on-action involves framing and reframing situations, self-evaluation, and is a deliberate process to understand past actions to direct future actions (Killen, 2016). The lecturers engaged in an individual structured self-reflection process at the end of the semester during the COVID-19 lockdown, guided by a collaboratively designed questionnaire. The four individual self-reflections were then subjected to an explicit critical review and qualitative analysis collaborated through the group's community of practice, in the form of online meetings, from which emerged the learnings in response to 'no student should be left behind,' 'save the academic year' and 'the new normal'. The experiences and reflections of the lecturers on teaching and learning during the lockdown period were consolidated and then subjected to content analysis to respond to the research questions. The questions in the questionnaire provided the key foci for content analysis within the Critical reflection-on-action study. Ethical protocols were followed

as the study was conducted under a research project registered in the Research Directorate at an institution of one of the lecturers.

Results and Discussion

Comparing approaches to the digital necessity during the COVID -19 pandemic

Aside from personal feelings expressed by the lecturers, lecturers expressed the impact of the pandemic on their professional roles. The key themes for comparison that emerged from the analysis were reflection, digitalization, response to ‘no student should be left behind’, participation and institutional support.

Reflections on rethinking pedagogy

The importance of the skill to reflect on-action and in-action is something that is taken for granted in teaching and learning. During times such as the pandemic, it has up-scored its significant role in the continuity and quality of the teaching and learning process. The lecturers had engaged in a reflective process which necessitated subsequent action, which is what is expected regularly for effective and quality teaching. The experiences show the deliberate initial reflection on teaching and learning involving both in-action and on-action reflection, albeit informally. The informal reflection, prompted by the COVID-19 pandemic and the subsequent lockdown, focused on digitalization for continuity of the academic year. Much of the initial efforts were individual voluntary introspection; rather than a prescribed approach by the institution. All four lecturers expressed the informal reflection on-action. The reflection encompassed communication with students, keeping pace with change, overall teaching philosophy and assessment.

L1: ‘I had to think about ways to communicate with students. I had to learn and upgrade myself on the use of technology in virtual teaching. I had to rethink assessment and communication to be fair to all students... The buzz word seemed to be on-line – but the reality came across as challenging. I had to download and learn about the platforms available to me as a lecturer’.

L4: ‘The pandemic has forced me to revisit my teaching pedagogy and philosophy. In the past, I preferred face-to-face teaching and incorporated technology quite minimally. The pandemic has upset the professional routine that I had become very accustomed to over the years’.

Digitalization

All the lecturers indicated that face-to-face engagement was the key mode of teaching and learning prior to the pandemic. Due to the pandemic, there was a sudden and immediate professional demand for digitalization in contrast to the previous predominant blended or face-to-face learning.

L2: ‘I had to rethink, re-orientate and reskill myself so that I may make use of the Learning Management System (Moodle) and its necessary tools effectively. Previously, face to face lectures dominated however there was an urgency now for me to embrace the multi-modal approach to teaching and learning’.

Digitalization and virtual teaching and learning are not new concepts. However, digitalization and virtual teaching are characterized by fundamentals which include access to data, devices, platforms and skills in being able to access and use learning platforms. The lecturers candidly expressed that actual online digital competency for teaching and learning prior to lockdown was minimal. The use of learning platforms was previously limited to asynchronous teaching and learning i.e. for student communication and posting of notes and tasks.

L4: ‘No. Not with teaching but I have used the learning platform - the institutional online learning platform - primarily for lecture notes, tutorials, guidelines, revision, exam/test papers, assessment reviews’.

All registered students had academic accounts linked to the official university teaching and learning portal and therefore had access to the learning platforms. However, synchronous teaching and learning during the initial period of the lockdown was evidently absent.

Response to ‘no student should be left behind’

In the early stages of the pandemic in South Africa, the National Minister for Higher Education had made a categorical assertion over the national television network that ‘no student should be left behind’ due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The reflective analysis elucidated below shows the lecturer’s efforts within their contexts to heed the call of the minister.

The responses categorically indicated that student on-line attendance was not comparable to the maximum success of attendance at face-to face lectures. However, one lecturer indicated the tendency of attendance to improve due to support factors viz. institutional support.

L1: 'Initially poor, 45% but gradually increased to about 63% but never over 80% unlike face-to-face'.

L4: 'At the start of the pandemic attendance was very poor...improved with institutional support in the form of data and laptops'.

Three of the four lecturers responded that they think they managed to achieve the call of 'no student is to be left behind'. This is notwithstanding their responses of the lack of hundred percent or close to thereof of student attendance. However, one lecturer who responded 'yes' indicated that achievement of 'no student is to be left behind' was for task submission and not for on-line class discussion and learning. It was evident that the lecturer placed emphasis on the process of learning and not only on the product of learning. One lecturer was of the opinion that it was not possible to achieve 'no student is to be left behind' as students were challenged with commitment and responsibility for their learning as well.

L2: 'Irrespective of the numerous attempts 'no student should be left behind' was not achievable and practical as students themselves struggled to take responsibility'.

All four lecturers used strategies, some common, to work towards the achievement of 'no student is to be left behind' within their contexts. The common approaches were largely asynchronous online learning which included recorded lessons, making printed notes available, posting on learning platforms, using a range of technological communication channels and allowing many opportunities for submissions and re-assessments. There was overt expression of human emotional skills such as patience and being non-judgemental in the learning process, compassion to students' backgrounds and contexts and the flexibility to accommodate students. The human element was categorically evident.

L1: 'Giving these students an opportunity to submit without being judgemental, as students home contexts were different. It took much patience'.

L3: 'Understanding that this pandemic was as a surprise to everyone, some degree of leniency was afforded to students, particularly regarding submission deadlines'.

Table 1 below shows some variation in approaches, although some may appear to be subtle. For example, Lecturer 1 (L1) restructured the course notes to overcome technological challenges of the large file size. Lecturer 1 also sought the assistance of students to mitigate lack of technological skills in using mobile devices by converting files for access on mobile devices. Lecturer 1 also used a pedagogic strategy of using group work in the teaching and learning process. Lecturer 2 expressed the extreme effort undertaken to contact students and perseverance in attempting to contact the next of kin, within a context of large numbers of students. Both Lecturers 2 and 4 indicated departmental efforts to include all students. Lecturer 2 indicated the departmental efforts to deliver notes to students across the province. Lecturer 3 indicated the extreme flexibility in submitting tasks in the forthcoming semester. The latter situation obviously raises questions of the administrative processes for concluding the semester or the parallel conduction of semesters. In addition, Lecturer 3 indicated that students were given the choice to use alternate learning platforms.

Table 1. Variations in efforts to achieve 'no student is to be left behind'

Lecturer	Approach to 'no student is to be left behind'
L1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The notes were restructured to get the salient points across to make the files smaller for attachment to messages. • Some students were helpful and used their technology skills to convert files to accessible formats on the mobile phone. • Group work also assisted in certain tasks as students communicated in smaller numbers viz. 5-6.
L2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With 436 registered students, approximately 100 students irrespective of numerous measures and attempts did not form part of the group. • Students were personally contacted, it was noticed that their contact details were incorrect, attempts were then made to locate their next of kin. • The faculty had prepared approximately 1600 study materials packages which were delivered to students in different parts of the province.

L3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Also, regarding submission of assignments, students who might be having issues with one online platform were allowed and actually encouraged to engage the lecturer on another platform.
L4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Our department has made a concerted effort to ensure that 'no student' should be left behind. Students who might have performed poorly as a result of poor technology, were given a chance to submit semester one assessment tasks in semester two.

The responses of the lecturers also highlight the challenges experienced within different contexts and the ways in which lecturers responded. The challenges will be discussed later on.

Active on-line participation

One of the fundamental principles for effective teaching and learning is active participation of the learner, which is learner-centred more especially within a constructivist learning paradigm. After the initial challenges, there was some shift to synchronous online teaching. The lecturers used different strategies to encourage student participation both in synchronous and asynchronous teaching and learning. Logging on did not necessarily mean active participation. A student may be logged on but engaged in some other activity outside of the lesson focus. For this reason, just the number of students logged on is actually a weak indicator of online learning success. However, irrespective of the number of students, although a hundred percent log on would be the ideal, the quality of participation is a better reflection of the effectiveness of the online learning experience. No teaching strategy is best in all circumstances, there is a need to make contextual decisions to use the ones most likely to achieve the learning outcome (Killen, 2016). The lecturers used different strategies to encourage online participation of students as indicated in Table 2.

Table 2. Strategies indicated to encourage active on-line participation

Lecturer	Strategies used
L1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I also encouraged students to ask questions or seek clarification I encouraged active learning by giving students little tasks, as I would in lectures? ...for example draw a mind map/flow diagram to show the key concepts and then randomly questioned.
L2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I also made use of the forum activity on Moodle which enables participants to have asynchronous discussions. I also used the Standard Forum, as this type of forum is open, encouraging any student to post their response or to start new topics at any time with the purpose of encouraging participation and dialogue between students I made use of a variety of activities in an attempt to encourage participation, I uploaded whiteboard animation power point presentation accompanied by activities that a student would need to complete after watching the presentation.
L3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I would give them assignments that requires them to research information online. I would also organise online discussion session and assign each student a topic to discuss. These discussions was one of the best exercises that were most appreciated by students because it test the knowledge about the subject and it sparks constructive debates.
L4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> By focusing mainly on the assessment tasks. The incentive of being awarded 2% more in the final CAM mark if there is on-line participation and completion of set tasks and quizzes. Posting frequent and timeous announcements of online lectures and tutorials

Aside from the typical question and answer strategy, lecturers indicated other strategies to actively engage the students during asynchronous and synchronous online learning, when conducted. Strategies during synchronous online included tasks prior to the session, tasks during the session and motivation for participation through the

incentive of being awarded marks. Lecturer 1 asked students to develop mind-maps/flow diagrams followed by random questioning during synchronous learning. The obvious disadvantage was that although tasks were given, unlike in face-to-face learning, it was not possible to monitor whether all students actually engaged in the process as lessons were audio based and verification was not immediately possible. Asynchronous active learning, included, as indicated by Lecturer 2, discussion forums and responses to video presentations posted on the learning platform. Lecturer 3, for some online synchronous sessions, tasked students to prepare in advance and present their tasks during the online session. A flipped classroom approach was used. Student response was positive to this approach. Lecturer 4 focused on assessment tasks and provided a two percent mark incentive for online participation. The researchers caution that, while there were efforts to encourage online participation, there were limitations with technical logistics such as data and internet connectivity, notwithstanding that some students had inadequate access to the learning platforms.

In spite of all the efforts to encourage online participation of students (as indicated in Table 2), all lecturers indicated challenges to getting students to participate actively. Categorically participation became a dichotomy of logging on and actual pedagogical engagement, with both being problematic.

L4: 'A number of students had to be forced to participate. Students appeared to be shy or nervous about the new and different mode of participation, especially in Zoom lesson. Delivery of on-line lessons were often teacher-centred'.

This challenge obviously questions the quality of student learning, in spite of efforts of the lecturers, in response to the call of 'no student is to be left behind'.

Asynchronous learning: Recorded lessons

Recordings, pre-recordings, videos and postings are asynchronous aspects of online learning (virtual). The responses of lecturers L2 and L4 below are quite loaded in that they bring out different aspects of teaching and learning viz. equality in the education process in relation to 'no student is to be left behind' and the shift of autonomy and responsibility of learning to students. The lecturers below show a clear distinction between recording a synchronous lesson (L4) and the use of a pre-recorded lesson (L2).

L2: 'Due to the lack of connectivity and data costs only 10% of students participated in synchronous lectures on BigBlue Button thus I then changed to recording asynchronous lectures on screen-castify and uploading on Moodle'.

L4: 'There were concerns that power outages in some suburbs impacted on students' on-line participation. Students preferred to have the Zoom lessons recorded so they could observe them in their own schedule. This was not necessarily a good idea as it prevented students from real-time participation'.

Recorded lessons seem to assist circumvent the interruption of the electricity supply within the South African context during synchronous online lessons. The interruption in the electricity supply would mean a break in continuity or the complete missing of a lesson. The impact in the case of the lecturer means that the lesson would need to be rescheduled if not recorded. The usefulness of pre-recorded lessons becomes evident. However, the assertion by Lecturer 4 that students preferred to observe the lesson in their own time means that the COVID-19 online learning was giving students an opportunity or choice to select their learning time. Face-to-face lectures were never recorded for future reference in the case of the four lecturers in this study. Face-to-face learning mandated students to be physically present, which does not necessarily mean to be intellectually present. Synchronous online lessons do make the recording of the lecture possible and available for future reference. This is an advantage to the lecturer and the student. The lecturer may use the recording for critical reflection of the lesson, to review student participation and understanding, and to assess students if the lesson was so designed. However, there was a reservation expressed in that recorded lessons may negate the real-time participation in discussions.

Institutional support

The start of the pandemic showed an initial lag in institutional support which improved with time. Institutional support was offered through departmental preparation and delivery of study material and the institutional promise of data and devices, as previously mentioned.

Further, institutional efforts to provide training workshops on the online training platform were evident.

L2: 'There was a need for us to be retrained as academics since in March we had a new version of Moodle, thus virtually we had training sessions per faculty broken up into different phases'.

Lecturer 1 indicated that there was institutional support in terms of developing skills to use the learning platform and availability of personnel to support the use of the learning platform, however, this was activated much later during the lockdown period.

L1: 'Aside from Departmental meetings, and a professional chat group for communication on administrative matters, communication with colleagues on teaching and learning issues were informal and unstructured. Informal discussions on sharing ideas on coping with the 'new normal' of on-line teaching was often spontaneous during mobile conversations on other agendas. However, later on the teaching and learning unit organised training on the use of the learning platform and the provided support by making personnel available during a certain time on weekly basis for specific development and assistance'.

The response shows that much was taken for granted by the lecturer and the institution in the use of online learning platforms prior to the pandemic. Weekly institutional support was prompted by the digital necessity of the pandemic, not as a proactive evolutionary process of encouraging online teaching and learning prior to the pandemic.

What were the key challenges to the digital necessity to teaching and learning?

The literature has reported on challenges to the digital necessity in different countries, mainly in first world ones. However, in this study challenges are reflected within the context of a country and the 'newness' of the digital experience to masses of students (from historical contact institutions) and with social and political inequalities of the past which manifest either subtly or categorically. In this paper, three challenges amongst the many that emerged are highlighted viz. online etiquette, limitations to teaching and learning and 'too many platforms'.

Online etiquette

While common problems such as access to devices, access to internet connectivity and unstable connectivity were raised, the question of on-line etiquette presented itself when log on was achieved. Etiquette is practised in the usual face-to-face teaching and learning context, for example the written or unwritten rules or guidelines for passive or active engagement in the teaching and learning context. The reflective analysis indicates that these rules cannot be taken for granted. The physical home background and digital technology literacy provided a challenge to the learning context in the form of disruptions in parallel with time limitations of online teaching.

L1: 'I had to educate students on on-line etiquette – switching video and audio off when not communicating, using the chat box and raising your hands to give a response. There were occasions where private background conversations could be heard and were disruptive, one had to pause until the individual/s could switch off. This hindered the flow of lessons and was time consuming. This is also showed the distractions to online learning that some students faced within their contexts and the unpreparedness for the shift from face-to-face learning to online learning'.

One must also take cognisance of the fact students use various devices with different levels of advancement, features and sizes. It is not always easy to locate the various features of raising one's hands or muting and unmuting. While the lecturer raises the concern within the framework of etiquette, a factor of influence could be the device itself and the lack of skill in using the device. The latter highlights the challenges.

Various limitations to teaching and learning

Effective online teaching and learning requires more than just digital literacy. It requires in-depth digital skills as well and full functionality of the online learning platforms. Lecturers' shortcomings and inadequate functionality of the platforms constrained the teaching and learning process as demonstrated by L1.

L1: 'Further, the kinds of questions that could be set on the system were limiting due to my own shortcoming of using the technology outside of multiple-choice questions. Also having tried a few other alternates the system was what I consider 'cumbersome' has it did not have all the features activated. I had to send students via the group chat, photographs of the assessment tasks'.

Student submission of work, assessment and feedback were identified as challenges to online learning. Firstly, inability to follow submission guidelines and the use of 'unconventional' strategies presented a time consuming challenge to filing of work by the lecturer and providing feedback to students. This must also be interpreted

within the context of large enrolment of students in courses and the number of continuous assessment tasks given to students. There was a marked difference in how two lecturers from different universities approached marking. Lecturer L1 developed a marking schedule for electronic submissions, with no comments being inserted on the student answers as the submission format presented a challenge. Lecturer L2, on the other hand, downloaded and printed the answer sheets and marked the hard copies. Lecturer 2 had previously indicated having 436 students in the module taught. The differences in approach show how the lecturers adapted to digitalisation. One continued to print and mark submissions as opposed to making maximum use of the option of digital assessment/marketing tools.

L2: 'With regard to the individual assignments, simply receiving them through emails and acknowledging each student's submission was a rather tedious process. I had decided to save the assignments in a folder and then print the assignments and mark the hard copies instead'.

Feedback is an essential iterative component for effective teaching and learning. The two different ways of marking shown by L1 and L2 impact on the quality of feedback. One set of students at one university had a marked hard copy, while at another university, students received a schedule with just the marks for the questions. In the latter, no individual feedback for the task was provided as the lecturer experienced difficulties with the format of submissions.

L1: 'Some of the photos were not clear and the formats varied for example of pdf it was not possible to insert comments. Hence, I had to develop a marking schedule with all students and insert a mark for the question numbered on the schedule. Individual feedback was not possible as it would have taken almost three times more time to mark on-line. Collective feedback was communicated together with the marking memorandum for students to review their work. Queries and clarification were however negotiated to the benefit of the student'.

However, one lecturer indicated that the use of the learning platform was useful as the system could be set to mark and provide the students with the correct answer, hence feedback was immediate (L3). However, there are limitations, as the system is only able to mark and provide immediate feedback to certain types of questions viz. multiple choice, true and false, fill in the blanks. Longer paragraph responses and discussion type questions had to be assessed by the lecturer.

Technology and connectivity are pivotal to online teaching and learning. Lecturers expressed their opinions and experiences related to technology and connectivity. Amongst them are the limitations for assessment (L1 and L4), the dominance of asynchronous learning (L2) and the extension of submission deadlines (L3).

L3: 'Late submissions – students would site data and network issues for not submitting on time. To work around this, I would extent a deadline, or ask a student which platform is more preferred to them'.

It is clearly evident that technology and connectivity issues are universal problems, including the context of this study. However, within the constraints of technology and connectivity, there was questionable student manipulation of the system resulting in compromises being made by the lecturers to achieve equality in student submissions. South Africa experiences periodic power outages (load shedding) to cope with demands of the electricity supply, sometimes with short notice, if any at all. However, a valid point is elucidated in the quotation of Lecturer L3 in relation to choice of learning platform. Just like assessment outcomes need to be transparent to students, student skill in using platforms for assessment are essential if assessments are to be valid and reliable i.e. if the assessment is to be considered a true reflection of the student's academic performance.

Too many platforms

Using different learning platforms within the institution or modules can be an advantage when alternates are needed. Respondents in a study focusing on school teachers in New Zealand and Australia indicated that due to different functionalities available in learning platforms, there was no single one which suited their needs as instructors (Flack, et al. 2020). Two of the lecturers in this study indicated that they used other learning platforms, aside from the official university one, while two did not. While using more than one platform can be considered an acceptable educational effort on the part of lecturers to increase student access to online learning, there are disadvantages. There is the over-burdening of students and the creation of confusion. In a way this devalues the official university learning platform.

L1: 'Students also complained about too many platforms. Feedback from students was the use of four different learning platforms across five modules. There was also preference to learning platforms which were not necessarily the official university learning platform'.

L3: 'My issue is that as academics we use different online teaching platforms and that confuses the students sometimes. I believe that if blackboard is the platform we use, then all of us should use that platform so that students can get everything they need in one place. Because if I use blackboard, someone else is using Moodle, and another Google Classroom, this confuses the student. So as academic it important to engage each other and decide on the right online teaching and learning platform to be adopted by the department'.

As previously expressed by Lecturer 1, some students indicated that they lacked skills to navigate the platforms to do online assessment tasks. The use of multiple platforms by different lecturers within the same program is likely to exacerbate the issue of platform navigation and may possibly work contrary to equality and quality to online teaching and learning in the 'new normal'.

Discussion

The efforts to continue teaching and learning in Higher Education in this comparative reflective study were both individual and collaborative during the digital necessity of the COVID-19 pandemic. This study reveals that the education system did not collapse but stimulated a courageous effort to overcome the departure from traditional face-to-face teaching and learning as usual contexts to predominantly online contexts. While there were myriad of challenges exacerbated by existing socio-political inequalities, opportunities for metacognitive reflection of teaching and learning, personal and professional transformation and the need for innovativeness subtly and categorically, in some cases, manifested. If anything, a more sustained response to education success during the forced digital necessity was evident rather than a collapse or standstill of education during the pandemic.

Comparatively, how did lecturers from different universities approach the digital necessity during the COVID-19 pandemic?

The results indicate that in reality online teaching was not implemented in the true sense but rather forms of technology were used which largely favoured asynchronous teaching and learning during the initial lockdown. In this study, none of the lecturers had any in-depth training in Information Systems and Technology. Thurman (2019) defined online learning as learning experiences involving both synchronous or asynchronous environments using devices with access to internet. On the other hand, other research evidence (Czerniewicz, 2020; Hodges, et al. 2020) considers online teaching and learning as adopting a computer-based distance education delivery model, yielding much flexibility considering the diverse environments during the teaching and learning process. Lecturers have indicated that given the inevitable need to continue with the academic calendar and to ensure that all students are given fair opportunity, mobile technology apps, email, printed material and physical delivery of notes were some of the strategies used. Asynchronous strategies seemed to be initially dominant and as in the case of one lecturer, became the key strategy to online teaching and learning. All students had academic accounts on the official university online learning platforms which differed among the universities in the study. In three universities in the study, learning platforms had limitations to live interactive discussions.

While the digital necessity was the envisaged strategy to continue the higher education programs, there was a mixed response to the reality of the assertion of 'no student is to be left behind'. In this regard various strategies were used, some common and some contextual. One of the lecturers adopted the approach of physical delivery of content notes. All the lecturers indicated online strategies to disseminate course content notes and for student task submission. Student task submission strategies included email, photographic and learning platform submissions. The 'new normal' encompassed more and flexible submission options for the students than the one submission option usually employed during face-to-face learning. As pointed out by Pather and Cupido (2020) transition involves a shift from unlearning old ways, rethinking ways of learning and adapting to new realities for online learning. This holds equally true where the individual student is valued more than just the online mode of learning to continue learning during a pandemic.

Integrating technologies in the educational process is more than having access to an internet connection (Chauhan, 2017). A valid point raised by one lecturer in response to 'no student is to be left behind' is the emphasis placed on the quality of the process of learning and not just the product of learning. In this regard this lecturer believed that 'no student is to be left behind' was not achieved. The three other lecturers described the submission of work by students and the flexibility of submission but student engagement in discussion was not

raised as priority. In essence, digital online learning should equally place emphasis on student engagement (i.e. the process of learning) as much as on the product of learning (i.e. submission of tasks). Nonetheless, all lecturers made efforts to encourage student online participation with much challenge.

Distance study for students, especially from home commonly requires greater self-discipline and motivation to attend online lessons, particularly in the earlier period of getting accustomed to the shift to online learning (Aristovnik, et al. 2020). All lecturers expressed their increased patience and understanding of students' contexts and unusual demands of the sudden forced migration to online learning. This was also the case at a university in India, where it was found that patience, empathy, care and motivating students were additional skills used to manage the online learning process in the sudden shift to online pedagogy (Mishra, et al. 2020). In this study though, it was expressed by two of the lecturers, while students were given the benefit in the 'new normal', at times student reasons for non-submission of tasks such as helplessness in data access, internet connection and electricity interruptions were questionable, with additional demands placed on lecturers to reset tests and extend due dates. In an international study, it was reported the highest proportion of students (42.6%) responded that their workload significantly increased in the online shift to education (Aristovnik, et al. 2020). To accommodate students, one of the lecturers in this study used the strategy of redesigning content notes to focus on key concepts in an attempt not to overwhelm students and for the ease of communicating smaller digital files.

What were the key challenges to the digital necessity experienced by the lecturers in Higher Education?

Various challenges were identified in this study. The common technical challenges included access to data, internet, devices and/or electricity. One of the initial key challenges was the lack of skill to use the available technology. As in the case of studies done by Kajjita et al. (2020) in universities in South Africa, this study also showed a limitation in skills to use digital technology for synchronous online learning. The traditional face-to-face learning had been the previous comfort zone, disrupted by the onset of the pandemic.

Digital technology in the form of online learning platforms in itself could become an impeding factor. Chauhan (2017) points out that crucial for integrating technologies in education is the close collaboration and shared vision amongst implementers of the use of the learning technologies. In this study, the concern was raised that there were too many learning platforms, aside from the official university platform being used by lecturers within the same department of the same university, obviously serving the same students. While exploring different learning platforms shows enthusiasm and innovativeness, it also devalues the official university learning platform. It was expressed that using various learning platforms also confused the students. Students need to account for passwords and have the technical ability to navigate the different sites to suit the different lecturers.

Challenges in student task submission, assessment and feedback were categorically identified by the four lecturers. Electronic assessment submission (e-submission) tools within learning platforms in higher education institutions overseas, such as in the United Kingdom, were the main centrally supported institutional tools prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (Voce, 2015). This was not the norm in the case at the institutions of the four lecturers in this study. Submission of tasks by students varied from institution to institution, with least mention via the official learning platform. Email, photograph submission using mobile messaging apps were the alternatives to platform e-submissions. The format of submission impacted on other aspects of assessment viz. marking and feedback. Feedback particularly in formative assessment provides specific comments on errors and misconceptions to the student (Killen, 2016). In this study, while formative assessment took priority in the final grading of students, individual and specific feedback in some cases was compromised. Lecturers expressed the challenge of providing this given the format of submission. Aside from the challenge of making comments on the electronic formats (photographic images of student work), lecturers also found this time-consuming and a strain on the human eye.

Sabzwari (2020), with reference to medical education, avers that in the uncertainty of the continuing crises, it is essential to develop multiple and creative ways of assessment to maintain quality and standards within the limitations of the pandemic. Lack of skill in using learning platforms and functional limitations presents a challenge to this creativity. One lecturer expressed the lack of skill to use a variety of question types on the platform thus limiting its use to multiple choice questions. On the other hand, the platforms were unable to automatically mark questions which required longer responses. These had to be downloaded or marked online. While there was multiplicity assessment i.e. in students doing practical tasks at home (for example identifying and drawing plants), doing online research tasks or doing assignments, submission formats and barriers were still present. For quality assessment standards to be maintained there is a dire need for trans-institutional engagement particularly with previous established distance education, non-contact institutions of learning. This

engagement should be at an institutional support level which is likely to have greater impact than individual lecturers negotiating their way in individual modules.

What are key factors associated with efforts to achieve quality and equality of teaching and learning to negotiate the digital necessity resulting from the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic?

In this study, the key factors associated with efforts to achieve quality and equality of teaching and learning to negotiate the digital necessity resulting from the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic can be identified as: personal and professional transformation (linked to reflection), innovativeness, skills development, understanding student contextual backgrounds, student participation, practical/field work and institutional and trans-institutional support.

Personal and professional transformation (linked to reflection): The COVID-19 crisis of mass lockdowns and quarantine necessitated the pedagogical shift from traditional method to online education from personal to virtual; it now seems with waves of resurgence e-learning and distance education are becoming predominant in the formal education system (Mishra, et al. 2020). Transformation is not always easy and is even more challenging when contexts are ‘imposed’ rather than aligned to gradual change. The Covid-19 pandemic prompted personal and professional transformation. Professional transformation involved a critical reflection of teaching and learning methodologies, being reflexive and embracing the shift to virtual teaching and learning, despite the challenges. Skills development became a co-factor in the transformation. All four lecturers indicated efforts to develop their virtual teaching and learning skills as a parallel process while virtual teaching and learning continued. In the commercial world the latter approach would be termed ‘on the job training’. The COVID-19 pandemic has pointed out the reality of the consequences of not developing with the pace of fundamental Information and Communications Technology (ICT) transformation processes in education and the need to deliberately provide professional development learning opportunities and training for those involved in teaching (Konig, et al. 2020).

Innovativeness and resourcefulness: Resourceful educators look for ways to overcome challenges, to facilitate learning to the advantage of students and make the most of limitations in conditions and opportunities available (Killen 2016). Embracing the ‘new normal’, all four lecturers in the reflective case study made efforts to rethink, adapt and try out what seemed new to them. An example is the use of ‘screencastify’ to develop videos for asynchronous online teaching. These efforts are indicative of the need to maintain or improve the quality of the learning experience. Self-efficacy became a decisive resource to adapt to online teaching during COVID-19 (Konig, 2020).

Understanding student contextual backgrounds: The case study clearly shows the attempt of lecturers to take into consideration student contextual backgrounds in the shift to virtual learning. The technological alternates to task submission, the extension of due dates and the resetting of assessment tasks were focal points that promoted efforts towards ‘no student is to be left behind’. Further, the human values of patience, understanding and perseverance were evident. Killen (2016) alludes to the point that compassionate educators are truly concerned about the welfare of learners and are empathetic.

Student participation: All four lecturers responded that student participation in online learning was a challenge. Quality education is dependent on student responsibility and participation. Participation is interpreted beyond ‘logging in’ but actively participating in lessons. Similar findings were also revealed from a study conducted with 762 students from two of the largest Romanian universities, whereby students lacked active learning, critical thinking skills and inability to debate and express their opinion during the online learning process (Coman, et al. 2020). The difficulties in synchronous lessons, where attempted, was that lecturers were unaware whether logged in students were attentive, although attempts were made to get students to answer. This is a contrast to face-to-face learning where students in the physical presence can be more closely monitored for participation in the learning activities. This challenge of student participation, raises two significant points. Firstly, was ‘no student is to be left behind’ in reality achieved? Secondly, the need for lecturers to be developed in strategies to get students to participate in online learning, more especially in synchronous learning. However, on a meta-level, what was achieved was the lecturers’ efforts and commitment to make ‘no student is to be left behind’ a reality.

Institutional and trans-institutional support: On an institutional level, if not a national level, there is need to reconceptualise the vision and mission of education to include a deliberate commitment to online pedagogies. The lecturers in this study indicated no previous commitment to online pedagogies. Chauhan (2017) alludes to the point that if technology is interwoven comprehensively into pedagogy, it can act as a powerful tool for

effective teaching and learning. Institutional support then needs to extend beyond the technical skills, to include and integrate the pedagogical skills, to use technology for online learning, for example, student active participation in learning activities and valid assessment practices. It was revealed in this study that institutional support for technological skills and online pedagogy was being stepped up at one university through the availability of teaching and learning personnel for categorical weekly consultations on lecturer specific enquiries, support and development. A study at a higher education institution in India on the online education shift during the pandemic, indicated that the ICT centre of the university convened several online sessions for familiarization with online tools and techniques and motivated teachers to attend technology-based teaching programmes conducted by other universities (Mishra, et al. 2020). These trans-institutional technology-based teaching programmes are coming to fruition in South Africa, albeit with some having financial attachments.

The meta-analysis of the informal trans-institutional reflective engagement of and by the four lecturers involved in this study was a revelation for pooling reflexive ideas for effective online pedagogy. As a result, lecturers were exposed to other pedagogical strategies that they had not individually considered previously within particular institutional contexts. For example, the flipped classroom approach indicated by one lecturer to increase effective online participation was tried out, with much success by another lecturer within the trans-institutional group. Within the unprecedented pandemic and contextual differences, there were opportunities to use similar pedagogies for quality education. Collegial trans-institutional support and engagement manifested some of these pedagogical opportunities.

Conclusion

The global COVID-19 pandemic has questioned and changed university teaching in ways never experienced before. The pandemic in a way provided an imperative for university lecturers towards reflexive practice and to modify their pedagogy. The complexities underpinning the shift to online learning at higher education institutions in varying contexts can in no way be undermined. The assertion of ‘no student is to be left behind’ overtly encouraged four lecturers, as may be the case with others, to negotiate their way to continue university teaching through the lockdown. As much as each of the lecturers was based in a different college/faculty and institution, there emerged a shared commonality in terms of experiences, challenges and adaptation to the digital learning space, in addressing the new normal and striving towards ‘no student left behind’. The challenges included inadequate competency to navigate learning platforms, pedagogical challenges of student participation amidst historical inequalities of data and device access and unstable interconnections. A conspicuous emergence was the emotional skills that fore-fronted and supported the student’s journey during the lockdown, shift to online learning and to the response of ‘no student is to be left behind’. However, while the lecturers displayed efficacy in their efforts, institutional and trans-institutional support emerged as significant co-factors to strengthen competencies and pedagogies to adjust to the ‘new normal’. Further to the personal and professional transformation, the meta-analysis of the informal trans-institutional engagement of the four lecturers has provided a satisfactory baseline from which to grow and mitigate the challenges of the shift to the ‘new normal’ of online learning. The collegial and professional conversations amongst the four lecturers prompted further reflective analysis manifesting in action to improve the quality of learning during the lockdown and augurs well for future endeavours. Despite rich learnings of the study, there are limitations which need to be acknowledged. Firstly, generalisability of results is limited due to varying institutional contexts and four participants. Secondly, the study was carried out in South Africa, therefore generalisation of results to educational contexts of other countries may not be necessarily be valid, although it may increase awareness or raise other questions on online learning. Despite geographical and economic differences, higher education institutions across the globe might have been unified with regard to the challenges arising from the pandemic.

Recommendations

Equality and quality are not confined to lecturers as facilitators of teaching and learning. It is a collaborative responsibility of primary stakeholders, viz. government ministries, higher education management, lecturers and students. The informal trans-institutional sharing has strong implications for professional development and virtual learning. Forming of trans-institutional and transdisciplinary ‘buddy groups’ serve to provide pedagogical and emotional support. The researchers further recommend both deliberate and informal active departmental conversations on online pedagogies to step up efficacy support for colleagues and more importantly to contextually enhance the quality of teaching and learning at higher education institutions.

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